

Some Studies on Swollen Head Syndrome in Broiler Chickens in Egypt

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Abstract

Swollen Head Syndrome (SHS) is a disease of upper respiratory tract affecting broilers and broiler breeders which resulted in inflammatory exudates beneath the skin. SHS has been described as a multi-factorial disease where the initial lesion mainly caused by avian Metapneumo virus (aMPV), while the clinical signs are a consequence of bacterial complications and the severity of the disease depends on environmental factors. This study was planned to detect and try to isolate the etiological agents of SHS from 40 broiler flocks in 3 Egyptian Governorates (Sharkia, Dakahlia and Damietta). The chickens incorporated swollen heads and respiratory manifestations as nasal discharges, coughing, tracheal rales and frothy conjunctivitis from different localities. Samples included trachea and lung tissues, choanal cleft swabs and scraps from sinuses and turbinates. The AMPV subtype B was detected in 5 flocks by Real Time Polymerase Chain Reaction (RRT-PCR) -using 2 specific probes for differentiation of subtypes A and B. the AMPV-subtype B was detected with the percentage of 12.5%. Bacterial examination of collected samples revealed presence of mixed infection in some of examined flocks with isolation of *E. coli* in a percentage of 70%; *Proteus mirabilis* 40% and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (25%). In conclusion, to our knowledge, this is the first detection of aMPV among broiler chickens suffering from SHS in Egypt, using RRT-PCR in concurrent bacterial infections with *E. coli*, *P. mirabilis* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Keywords: Swollen Head Syndrome, Broilers, Avian Metapneumo Virus.

Introduction

Swollen head syndrome (SHS) manifests a respiratory disease in chickens which is usually a multi-factorial and caused initially by a virus known as Pneumovirus [4].

The avian Metapneumo virus (aMPV) causes upper respiratory tract infection in turkeys and chickens causing increased mortality especially when combined with secondary bacterial infections. In chickens, aMPV infection is often associated with SHS [1-4]. However, the disease could not be reproduced with a MPV alone and chicken flocks can be infected without showing clinical signs.

The aMPV is classified in the genus Metapneumo virus, within the subfamily Pneumovirinae of the Paramyxoviridae family [5]. The aMPV genome consists of approximately 13 kb of negative single stranded RNA, encodes eight viral proteins which are: nucleo-capsid protein (N), phospho protein (P), matrix protein (M), fusion protein (F) which is expressed as a precursor protein

called Fo that is cleaved to produce F1 and F2, second matrix protein (M2), small hydrophobic protein (SH), surface attachment glycoprotein (G), and RNA-dependent RNA-polymerase (L) flanked by a leader and trailer at the 3' and 5' ends, respectively. Absence of two non-structural proteins (NS1 and NS2) found in the respiratory syncytial pneumoviruses, and the unique gene order of 3'-N-P-M-F-M2-SH-G-L-5' identifies aMPV and human Metapneumovirus (hMPV) as Metapneumo viruses [6]. Based on the G gene sequence AMPV strains can be characterized into genomic subtypes which are (A, B, C and D) [7].

The initial sign of SHS in broilers, was nasal sneezing "snick" within one day, which progressed to reddening of conjunctiva with swelling of lacrimal glands and peri-orbital sinuses that followed 12-24 hours by subcutaneous edema of the head which started around the eye then progress over the head and descend to the inter mandibular tissues and wattles within 24-36 hours whereas, individual

bird showed depression and disinclination to move. Few affected birds showed head shaking and hyper lacrimation. Some birds scratch their face with feet or rotate their necks and rub the peri-orbital area over the other aspect of their wings [5]. This study was planned to detect and try to isolate the etiological agents of SHS from 40 broiler flocks in 3 Egyptian Governorates.

Material and Methods

Field investigation

Forty broiler flocks showed SHS were examined with recording of history, clinical signs, morbidity and mortality rates and postmortem lesions.

Clinical samples

Samples were collected from non-vaccinated (i.e. no SHS vaccine) 40 commercial broiler flocks from 3 Egyptian Governorates (Sharkia, Dakahlia and Damietta) with respiratory signs. Samples were taken from lungs; trachea and cloacal cleft swabs and scrap from sinuses and turbinates then placed in PBS with addition of penicillin and streptomycin at a concentration of 1000 IU and 1mg/ml, respectively. Organs and swabs were transmitted on ice to the laboratory.

Positive control sample

A commercial vaccinal aMPV strain was used as a positive control in RRT-PCR. The vaccine commercial name is Nemovac L436453 of Merial- France.

RNA extraction

The viral RNA was extracted from pooled collected samples using QIAamp Viral RNA Mini kit (catalogue no.52906) (Qiagen).

RRT-PCR

One primer pair which is specific for SH gene were used with 2 different probes for detection and differentiation of aMPV subtypes A and B, the primers were designated as SHf and SHr where their sequences were 5'-TAG TTT TGA TCT TCC TTG TTG C -3' and 5'-GTA GTT GTG CTC AGC TCT GAT A- 3'; respectively. The 2 probes were designated as MB-SH-A and MB-SH-B and their sequences were 5'HEX-CGC GAT CGT GGA CCT CCT

GCA CTG TGG ATC GCG-Iowa Black® FQ 3' and 5'-FAM-CGC GAT CAT TGT GAC AGC CAG CTT CAC GAT CGC G-Iowa Black® FQ 3'; respectively. Two separate reaction mixtures were set up- for each sample - following the manufacturer's instructions of the Superscript III Platinum™ One-Step Quantitative RT-PCR System (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, California, USA) in a total volume of 25 µL for each: The first one contained 12.5 µL of Probe RT-PCR Master mix; 0.5 µL of Enzyme mix; 5 µL of Template RNA; 1 µl MgSO₄; 0.5 µL Primer aMPV-SHf; 0.5 µL Primer aMPV-SHr; 0.5 µL Probe A; 4.5 µL RNase-free water. The second reaction contained the same components except probe B was used instead of probe A. Thermal cycling conditions for aMPV subtypes A and B where 1 cycle of Reverse transcription for 30 min at 50°C; 1 cycle of Heat activation of polymerase for 2 minutes at 95°C; 40 cycles of PCR Denaturation at 95°C for 30 sec a, annealing at 57°C for 45 sec. with fluorescence data collected at the end of each annealing step [8].

Bacteriological isolation

Collection, handling and isolation of samples

Swabs were collected aseptically from subcutaneous edema and sinuses exudates and were immediately inoculated into nutrient broth, then incubated at 37°C for 24h then sub cultured on Nutrient agar and MacConkey agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 h.

Colonial morphology

The colonial characters were observed and described [9].

Vitek2 compact system

Fresh pure colonies were characterized and identified biochemically using the Vitek2 compact system following the manufacturer instructions (BioMerieux).

Molecular identification of E. coli by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

Bacterial samples suspected to be *E. coli* were screened for presence of 16s rRNA gene using specific primers [10] and the primers were designated as ECO-1-F and ECO-2-R and their sequences were 5'- GAC CTC GGT TTA GTT CAC AGA -3' and 5' CAC ACG CTG ACG CTG ACC A -3' respectively. The PCR

mix and cyclic conditions were applied [11]. Briefly the reaction mixture contained: 2 μ L DNA template; 1 μ L Taq DNA polymerase (IU/ μ L); 5 μ L of the 10X reaction buffer; 1 μ L of dNTPs; 1 μ L of 25 mM MgCl₂; 1 μ L of Forward primer (25 pmol); 1 μ L Reverse primer (25 pmol) and Double distilled water up to 50 μ L. The cycling condition was, Initial denaturation 95°C for 3 minutes, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 45 seconds, annealing at 58°C for 45 seconds and extension at 72°C for 1 minute followed by 3 minutes final extension period at 72°C. The PCR products were submitted to electrophoresis in 1.5% Agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide and visualized under UV trans-illuminator.

Results

Field investigation

History of examined flocks revealed swollen heads in about 3- 5% of the flocks at 23-32 days age. The observed clinical signs were coughing, snicking, wet or frothy eyes, conjunctivitis, sneezing, facial edema, unilateral or bilateral swelling of infra-orbital sinuses. Some chickens showed swelling of their entire face including wattles as illustrated in Figure 1. The recorded postmortem lesions revealed often yellowish extensive gelatinous to purulent edema of subcutaneous tissues in head region, sinusitis, tracheitis. In addition to, pericarditis, perihepatitis, tracheitis, pneumonia and air sacculitis were seen in complicated cases.

Detection and subtyping of aMPV using RRT-PCR

Five samples out of 40 were positive and confirmed as aMPV subtype B isolates as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: A Broiler chicken showing bilateral swelling of periorbital and infraorbital sinuses.

Figure 2: RRT-PCR results where the red line indicates the positive control sample while the green lines indicate positive samples and black line indicates negative control sample.

Isolation and identification of concurrent bacterial infections.

The recovered isolates from suspected samples on different media were characterized as *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *P. mairabilis*. The culture characters for each bacterial spp. Were as follows: *E. coli* showed turbid growth on nutrient broth, Circular, smooth surface colonies, mucoid and greyish in color on nutrient agar and pink colonies of lactose fermenter on MacConkey agar. On the other hand, the culture characteristics for *P. aeruginosa* appeared as abundant growth and turbidity with bluish green color on Nutrient broth, convex, glistening and translucent with bluish green color on Nutrient agar and pale colonies of non-lactose fermenter on MacConkey agar. Finally, the culture characteristics for *P. mirabilis* were uniform

turbidity with a slight powdery deposit and an ammoniac odor on Nutrient broth, swarms intermittently in the characteristic step-like pattern across agar surface on Nutrient agar and pale colonies of non-lactose fermenter on MacConkey agar.

Morphological characteristics of isolates

Colonies were gram negative, non sporulated, medium sized bacilli.

Molecular identification of E. coli isolates

28 samples out of 40 were positive for *E. coli* in a percentage of 70%.

PCR amplification of E. coli isolates

The genomic DNA of *E. coli* was tested using specific primers giving rise to a product of 585 bp as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Ethidium bromide-stained 1.5% agarose gel showing amplified products of 16S rRNA gene from *E. coli* isolates at 585 bp (M, marker; positive samples are 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7 and 9 while negative samples are 4, 8 and 10).

Vitek2 compact system results

Single and mixed infected samples were confirmed and revealed 28 isolates were *E. coli* with percentages of 70%, 16 isolates were

P. mirabilis with a percentage of 40% and 10 isolates were *P. aeruginosa* with a percentage of 25% as illustrated in Tables (1,2).

Table 1: Incidence of different bacterial isolates among SHS suspected cases of broiler chicken flocks.

Bacterial type	Tested flocks No.	Frequency of isolation	Percent of isolation	
<i>E. coli</i>	40	16	40%	
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	40	4	10%	
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	40	6	15%	
Mixed infections	<i>E. coli</i> + <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	40	4	10%
	<i>E. coli</i> + <i>P. mirabilis</i>	40	8	20%
	<i>P. mirabilis</i> + <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	40	2	5%

Table 2: Cumulative percentage of each bacterial isolate among SHS suspected cases of broiler chicken flocks.

Bacterial isolate	Percent of isolation
<i>E. coli</i>	70%
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	25%
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	40%

Discussion

Infection of respiratory tract has a significant economic impact on poultry production worldwide. Various pathogens have been known to cause respiratory disease acting either in a primary or a secondary role. aMPV is a respiratory virus that infects a range of avian hosts including chickens and turkey. Swollen head syndrome is a disease of upper respiratory tract and is considered as one of these problems in last few years. Moreover, there are several studies showed that viral and bacterial factors are involved in occurrence of this condition. So, clinicians have used the term respiratory complex to describe this syndrome [12].

The observed clinical signs of examined broiler flocks with swollen heads showed cough, wet eyes, conjunctivitis, sneezing, unilateral or bilateral swelling of infraorbital sinuses these results were nearly similar to previous findings [5,13-16].

The PM findings were yellowish gelatinous to purulent exudates in subcutaneous tissues of the head, besides pneumonia and air sacculitis in complicated cases. These findings agreed with those obtained by previous researchers [15,17-19]. In addition, we observed otitis externa and interna in the affected chickens, which are comparable by former results [20, 21].

Concerning the detection of aMPV using RRT-PCR our results revealed 5 positive samples out of the collected 40 samples (12.5%). The detected virus isolates belonged to subtype B of aMPV. Up to our Knowledge, this is considered the first report about detection of aMPV subtype B in broiler chickens in Egypt. Equivalent results were recorded in Egypt as TRT antibodies in broilers were detected from ten farms showing swollen heads and in other five healthy broiler farms in different Egyptian Governorates using two different ELISA kits indicating seroprevalence of the virus in Egypt [22]. Also, Mahmoud *et al.* and Arafa *et al.* [23,24] detected TRT virus (aMPV) from turkey flocks in Egypt of subtype B. Furthermore, our results were agreed with that of Banet-Noach *et al.* [25] who detected aMPV subtype B in 7

broiler flocks out of 133 examined flocks constituting about 12.5% of tested flocks in Jordan. Also, nearly same results were obtained in Iran [16] with a detection of aMPV subtype B in 8 samples out of 43 (18,6%) tested broiler flocks

Our results confirmed the occurrence of aMPV subtype B among poultry flocks in Egypt. These results are in agreement with Mahmoud *et al.* and Arafa *et al.* in Egypt [23, 24], Gharaibeh and Algharaibeh in Jordan [26] and Homayounfar *et al.* and Mansour *et al.* [16, 27] in Iran. Thus, indicating higher prevalence of aMPV subtype B in the Middle East.

The lower detection rate of aMPV from the affected broiler flocks may be due to short period of presence of virus in the tissues of affected birds -nearly not more than 4 days-, in addition to presence of secondary bacterial infection in most of affected cases. The same hypothesis was previously suggested [26].

Concerning concurrent bacterial infections, our results revealed detection and isolation of *E. coli* in about 70% of suspected cases, *P. mirabilis* 40% and *P. aeruginosa* 25%, either in single or mixed infections. These results are compatible with Goodwin and Waltman [29] results who isolated *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *P. mirabilis* and Staphylococcus from young chicken during 1992 with SHS and others [5, 29-30, 31] who isolated *E. coli* from cases of SHS and from nasal sinuses and tracheas of chickens suffering from respiratory troubles as well as McDougall and Cook [32] who isolated *E.coli*, *Moraxella* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp. from turkeys affected by TRT.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our results revealed detection of aMPV for the first time among broiler chickens in Egypt, using RRT-PCR, besides isolation and identification of *E. coli*, *P. mirabilis* and *P. aeruginosa* as complicating pathogens using Vitek2 compact system.

Conflict of interest

All the authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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الملخص العربي

بعض الدراسات على متلازمة تورم الرأس في بدارى التسمين

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تعد متلازمة تورم الرأس (SHS) مرض للجهاز التنفسي العلوي الذي يصيب بدارى وامهات بدارى التسمين والذي يؤدي إلى الإفرازات والتهاب تحت الجلد. وقد وصف (SHS) على أنه مرض متعدد الأسباب حيث يبدأ المرض بالأفة الأولية الناجمة أساساً عن فيروس الميتا الرئوى للطيور في حين أن الاعراض الأكلينيكية هي نتيجة للمضاعفات البكتيرية وتعتمد شدة المرض على العوامل البيئية. وقد تم التخطيط لهذه الدراسة للكشف عن ومحاولة عزل العوامل المرضية المسببة لمتلازمة تورم الرأس (SHS) من ٤٠ قطيع بدارى التسمين في ٣ محافظات (الشرقية والدقهلية ودمياط) بمصر. وبإجراء الفحص الإكلينيكي على الطيور المصابة بتورم الرأس وجد بها إفرازات من الأنف والعين والتهابات فى الملتحمة وتورم فى تجويف أحد أو كلا العينين وبعضها كان يعانى من تورم فى الدلايات وشملت العينات قصبه الهوائية والأنسجة الرئة، مسحات الشقوق المشقوقة والقصاصات من الجيوب الأنفية والتوربينات. بإستخدام زوجين من (probes) فى تفاعل البلمره المتسلسله قادرين على التمييز بين نوعى A و B من فيروسات الميتا الرئوى للطيور وعليه تم الكشف عن فيروس الميتا الرئوى فى الطيور من النوع B فى عدد ٥ قطعان بنسبه تواجد تمثل ١٢,٥%. كما كشف الفحص البكتيري للعينات التي تم جمعها وجود عدوى مختلطة فى بعض القطعان التي تم فحصها مع عزل الايشريشيا كولاي بنسبة ٧٠%. بروتيويس ميرابيليس ٤٠% و سيودوموناس أيروجينوسا (٢٥%). ومن هذه الدراسة نخلص على حد علمنا انه الكشف الأول عن وجود فيروس الميتا الرئوى للطيور فى بدارى التسمين التى تعانى متلازمة تورم الرأس في مصر متوامنا مع العدوى البكتيرية الايشريشيا كولاي و بروتيويس ميرابيليس و سيودوموناس أيروجينوسا .

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